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CORRELATIONS BETWEEN BEHAVIOR AND PRAGMATIC ABILITIES IN ADULTS WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS

1. Introduction

Pragmatic competence involves the skills that enable a person to integrate information during conversation and to monitor the mental states of the interviewee, such as: adequate use of language for various purposes, adaptation of language to context characteristics, adherence to conversational and narrative rules, reasoning, imagination, existence of communicative intent, adequate use of prosody, and the ability to match the message to the mental states of the interviewee. Discourse skills reflected in respect for social conventions and the ability to use linguistic and non-linguistic skills to begin and maintain a theme, to adapt the meaning and form to the listener, and to make appropriate use of non-verbal cues (Van der Lely 2003). Pragmatic abilities give us insight into the speaker's intentions, assumptions, and goals (Ivšac and Gaćina 2006). This phenomenon is particularly addressed by the Theory of Cognitive Pragmatics, (Bara 2011).

Pragmatics deficits in people with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) is related to deficits in the field of theory of mind. They are manifested by inability to adapt to the communicative situation, inadequate exchange of information during the conversation, ignorance of the rules of what role the speaker and interlocutor play in communication, atypical prosody, and literal interpretation of the transferred meanings (Martin and McDonald 2003). Also, research shows that people with ASD indicate difficulties in using pragmatic markers of time and space, reduced expression of mental states (Baron-Cohen 1988), use of inappropriate utterances and idiosyncratic gestures during storytell-

ing (Loveland, McEvoy, Tunali and Kelley 1990), and reduced complexity and number of causal statements (Terzić and Drljan 2011). People with ASD may be unsuccessful in adapting the story to the listener, may speak in the same manner with both friend and stranger, make irrelevant comments, and have difficulty interpreting indirect expressions (Tager-Flushberg and Sullivan 1995), difficulty in continuing conversations, insensitivity to other people's opinions, staying on one topic for too long, or being too embarrassed by small things (Attwood 1997). Difficult participation in social interactions and understanding of the world around them can lead to the manifestation or intensification of behavioral problems. Behavioral problems are often a reaction to environmental factors. The causes of negative emotions are cognitive and communication difficulties that limit the expression of feelings and the understanding of a stimulus. Difficulties in establishing an adequate relationship with the environment and understanding the world around them, as well as a sense of social inadequacy, can lead to the manifestation or intensification of behavioral problems (Beirne-Smith, Patton and Hill 2006).

Behavioral problems of people with ASD are one of the more significant problems. These problems impedes the acquisition of new adaptive skills and adversely affects the person's interaction with the environment. (Radovanović 2009).

2. Research methodology

2.1. Subject of research

The subject of our study is the impact of pragmatic competencies on behavioral problems in adults with ASD and whether sociodemographic characteristics such as gender, age, education, and residential type, as well as specific characteristics of respondents, influence their association.

2.2 Objectives of the research

The aim of the study was to examine pragmatic competencies and behavioral problems in adults with ASD, as well as the existence and nature of the relationship between the development of pragmatic language level and the occurrence of behavioral problems in this population. The extent of the presence of behavioral problems and the development of the pragmatic level of language were examined first, as well as the predictor role of pragmatic competencies, respondent characteristics and sociodemographic characteristics in relation to behavioral problems in adults with ASD.

2.3. Research procedure

The consent of the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Novi Sad was obtained, as well as the institutions where the parent / guardian's research and consent for the participation of their child/ protege were conducted.

Special education teachers of adults with ASD who have known the subjects for a minimum of 12 months was conducted Assessment of the development of pragmatic competencies, assessment of behavioral problems, and completion of the General Questionnaire on Socio-Demographic/Socioeconomic Characteristics of the family by subjects. Data on the specifics of the subjects condition were obtained on the basis of data available from the documentation of the institution. All respondents had an associated intellectual disability. People with other comorbid disorders were excluded from the study.

2.4. Sample description

The sample consisted of 50 subjects with autism spectrum disorders, from 24 to 45 years, with a slightly higher percentage of the sample being men (78%). The mean age of the sample was 34.5 years (SD = 5.65). Majority of the sample (66%) have primary school, 10% have no school. The highest percentage of respondents belongs to the category of moderate intellectual disability (54%). The largest percentage of respondents live in an institution (54%), the remaining respondents live with parents. When it comes to parental education, 68% of respondents say they have a high school diploma while the rest have a college or university degree. About 52% of respondents are non-verbal.

2.5. Research instruments

- *The Pragmatic Profile of Everyday Communication Skills in Adults* (Dewart and Summers 1996) was used to assess pragmatic competences. The instrument contains 28 questions, grouped into 4 areas: Communication Functions, Communication Response, Interaction and Conversation, and Contextual Variations. Each item scores with respect to the frequency of occurrence of grades 1 to 5, where a score of 1 indicates that a certain behavior never occurs, while a score of 5 indicates that a certain behavior always occurs, indicating greater severity of pragmatic functioning problems.

The Communicative Function area gives an insight into the primary expression modules of communicative functions, whether a person communicates in a number of different ways or if only one module is present.

The Communication Response area tells us whether a person responds to a communication or some aspects of communication present difficulties in understanding them.

The area of Interaction and Conversation is about participation in social interactions, how to initiate and maintain communication.

The Contextual Variation area provides information about the circumstances in which a person is most likely to communicate, or in which he or she has the most difficulty.

The instrument has been constructed as an integrative method for the assessment of pragmatic competencies in adults with aphasia, learning disabilities, autism spectrum disorders, hearing impairment, mental health problems and other groups such as dementia. By calculating the Kronbach's alpha coefficient, the Pragmatic profile of everyday communication skills proved to be excellent $\alpha = 0.977$.

- *The Behavior Problem Checklist* (Tyrer, Nagar, Evans, Oliver, Bassett, Liedtka and Tarabi 2016) is intended to assess the behavior problems of persons with intellectual disabilities. The questionnaire is completed by professionals (special educators) who have been involved in working with respondents for more than 12 months. It is divided into seven areas:
 - personal violence, violence against others and includes verbal and physical forms of violence;
 - objective violence, destruction of material inventory;
 - self-harming behavior, stereotypical behavior, skin damage, to serious self-harming behavior;
 - sexually objectionable behavior, directed at others or towards oneself, verbal and physical forms;
 - defiant behavior, from verbal negativism to pronounced defiant behavior;
 - demanding behaviors, ranging from less disturbing (often attention-grabbing) to more disturbing behaviors,
 - running away.

Each of the aforementioned areas is rated 1 to 5 and a higher grade also implies a higher degree of behavioral problems. Reliability The behavior checklist is excellent, $\alpha=0.967$.

- General questionnaire

The general questionnaire was created for this research with the purpose of obtaining general information about the respondents: age, gender, residential type, education of the respondents, education of parents, data on intellectual abilities from the documentation of the institution.

3. Results

3.1. Results of the assessment of pragmatic competences

The results show that for both the total score and the subdomains of the questionnaire used, the distribution corresponds to a normal distribution. The results of analysis of variance for dependent samples show that there are statistically significant differences in the expression of different pragmatic competences. Posthoc analysis shows that, with respect to the remaining three competencies, the best competencies are related to contextual variation ($F=45,124$; $p=0.000$).

3.2. Results of behavioral problems assessment

The analysis conducted indicates that for the total score and within the subdomain of the questionnaire used, the distribution corresponds to a normal distribution (values below ± 1.5). From the results obtained, it is concluded that behavioral problems are mild in persons with ASD. The results of analysis of variance for dependent samples show that there are no statistically significant differences in the expression of different behavioral problems. All tested aspects of behavioral problems were equally represented ($F=2,085$; $p=0.074$).

3.3. Results of examining the predictive role of pragmatic abilities on behavior problems

To examine whether pragmatic competencies are a significant predictor of behavioral problems in adults with ASD, Pearson's correlation was conducted and the results show that the association between these variables is significant and negative ($r=-0.34$, $p=0.01$). Multiple regression analysis was applied to determine more precisely which part of the variance in behavioral problems can be explained by the variance of different pragmatic competences. The set of predictors consisted of four pragmatic competencies, and the criterion variable consisted of the total score on the Behavior Problems Scale.

Multiple correlation analysis showed that 78.1% of the variance in behavioral disorders can be explained by a disorder in pragmatic competences.

Significant individual contribution to prediction is achieved by the variables Communicative Functions, Interaction/Conversation, Contextual Variations.

All relationships are negative, with a slightly higher individual contribution to prediction (beta coefficient), the interaction/conversation variable. Thus, individuals with more of these three pragmatic competencies have less pronounced behavioral problems.

3.4. Examination results of the predictor role of sociodemographic factors in relation to pragmatic competences and behavioral problems

There are no gender differences even when looking at subscales. The same results were obtained when it comes to differences between respondents living with parents and those placed in institutions ($t=1,001$; $p=0,322$).

Pearson's linear correlation coefficient was applied to determine whether there is a correlation between age and level of intellectual ability with pragmatic competencies and behavioral problems. The results show that there are no statistically significant correlations between pragmatic competencies and behavioral problems with respondents' age. When considering the relation between pragmatic competences and behavioral disorders with the degree of intellectual disability, there are three statistically significant correlations of moderate to high intensity, correlation with behavioral disorders ($r=0.604$; $p<0.00$), with the domain of interactions/conversations ($r=-0.334$; $p<0.01$) and the domain of contextual variation from the pragmatic competence framework ($r=-0.449$; $p<0.01$). Such results suggest that the more severely impaired a person is, the greater the degree of behavioral problems and poorer pragmatic competences in the domains of contextual variation and interaction/conversation.

4. Discussion

The results of our research show that people with ASD exhibit significant problems in the field of pragmatic functioning, most in the area of Interaction/Conversation, Response to Communication and Communication Functions, while the best results are achieved in the field of Contextual Variation.

Various authors (Tager-Flushberg, Paul and Lord 2015; Young, Diehl, Morris, Hyman and Bennetto 2005) argue that persons with ASD have the most problems with language skills that require the use of language in a flexible, rational manner in all communicative circumstances, and confirm that the main problem with persons with ASD is in the field of pragmatic language.

Some authors state that people with ASD have the most difficulty starting and holding a conversation, as well as knowing how much information

to share with others (Tager-Flusberg, Paul and Lord 2015; Volden, Coolican, Garon, White and Bryson 2009). In their research, Baron-Cohen, Wheelwright, Skinner, Martin and Clubley (2001) stated that they had the most difficulty with ASD in the field of narrative discourse. These results are consistent with ours, which showed that our respondents exhibit the most problems exhibiting on the Interaction / Conversation subscale, which is exactly what the area of narrative discourse implies.

Nagai, Hinobayashi and Kanazama (2017) state that people with ASD share less emotion with other people, avoid eye contact, and have difficulty predicting the future. These behaviors are contained in the Communication Functions subscale of the profile we used, where respondents showed significant discrepancies.

Various authors (Happe and Charlton 2012; Loukusa, Leinonen, Kuusikko, Jussila, Mattila, Ryder, et al. 2006) state that persons with ASD have difficulty understanding metaphors, jokes, ironies, indirect speech acts, and conversational interferences. We have also examined these domains, which are contained in the Response to Communication subscale, and our findings confirm that persons with ASD exhibit problems in this area.

Hermann, Haser, Van Elst, Ebert, Muller-Felmedth, Riedel, et al. (2013) compared adults with ASD and their neurotypical peers in understanding metaphors and stated that there were no statistically significant differences. This result differs from our results, but the authors included persons with high-functioning autism in their sample, while in our work, the sample was mostly composed of persons with moderate intellectual disability in addition to ASD. This confirms that the coefficient of intelligence is a significant predictor factor in the manifestation of pragmatic competences.

Various authors (Chow and Wehby 2018; Boones, Majjars, Lambrechts, Zink, Van Leeuwen and Noens 2014) report that adults with ASD have more behavioral problems than people in the general population. It has been observed in adults with ASD that the most common problems are anxiety and depression, obsessive-compulsive disorder, attention problems and hyperactivity, and defiant behavior (Skokauskas and Gallagher 2010). Numerous studies indicate that age plays a large role in manifesting behavioral problems in this population (Talijan 2015; Wise, Smith and Rabins 2017). Our results show mild behavioral problems in the subjects. However, 90% of our respondents have associated psychiatric illnesses and take medication, which in turn results in less manifestation of psychopathological symptomatology. Also, the

difference between our results and others can be explained by the fact that our respondents are either on institutionalized type of accommodation or regularly attend a social welfare institution where experts are employed, who are continuously providing them with the necessary support. These results support the results of Weiss, Smith and Rabins (2017), whose sample reduced behavioral problems through one year of rehabilitation support.

4.1. The influence of pragmatic competences on behavioral problems

The results of our study show that the level of development of pragmatic competences plays a significant predictor role in the manifestation of behavioral problems. Variables Communicative Functions, Interaction/Conversation, Contextual Variations have a significant individual contribution to prediction, with a slightly higher individual contribution to prediction being the Interaction/Conversation variable, which proved to be the most damaging in our respondents. In his research on the pragmatic profile of people with low-functioning autism, Talijan (2015) states that 48.9% of respondents exhibit some form of maladaptive behavior as a form of expressive communication. Also, almost half of the respondents exhibited behavioral problems in distressing or incomprehensible situations to other people.

That pragmatic difficulties are associated with externalized behavioral problems is supported by studies showing that individuals with ASD spectrum who have problems with pragmatic functioning have a greater tendency to act aggressively than those with better pragmatic competencies (Boonen, Majjars, Lambrechts, Zink, Van Leuween and Noens 2014; Chow and Wehby 2018; Nagai, Hinobayashi and Kanazama 2017).

Matson and Cervantes (2014) state that communication and behavioral problems are causally related, that is, communication deficits affect a person's ability to interact socially with others, and that reductions in social interactions lead to an inability to learn and practice new pragmatic competencies.

In their study, Rodas, Eisenhower and Blacher (2017) explain the mechanism of anxiety development by the fact that children with pragmatic impairments may misunderstand others in the social setting, which may cause difficulties in achieving social goals, and consequently lead to anxiety. One of their findings is that individuals with better pragmatic competencies have less anxiety and fewer behavioral problems, and that pragmatic competency-oriented interventions and functional communication training can also help reduce behavioral problems (Rodas, Eisenhower and Blacher 2017). Limited pragmatic compe-

tence competences affect behavioral problems and, by reducing self-control capacity, those frustrated by language constraints may become aggressive and depressed when unable to understand others and express themselves, develop problems in emotional and psychosocial adjustment.

4.2. Predictor role of sociodemographic factors

Sociodemographic factors whose predictor role was examined by gender, age, housing status, respondents' education, parents' education, and respondents' intellectual abilities. The results of our study show that the strong predictor factors were the level of intellectual disability and the level of education of the respondents.

In their study comparing gender differences in pragmatic competence in persons with ASD, (Conlon, Volden, Smith, Duku, Zwaigenbaun, Waddell, et al. 2019) found that there were differences in individual segments, such as narrative production, where female persons were observed to be more fluent and give more relevant comments from the male, as well as paying more attention to the speaker's intentions, are more skillful at maintaining focus and making their stories more comprehensible. However, they emphasize that there is no difference in overall achievement related to pragmatic competencies, which is consistent with our findings and those of numerous other studies (Kauschke, Van der Beek and Kamp-Becker 2016; Pisula, Pudlo, Slowinska, Kawal, Strzaska, Banasiak and Wolanczyk 2017). However, it has been found that there is a significant gender difference in behavioral problems. Females exhibit more internalizing problems in the field than males and (Solomon, Van Wijngaarden, Van Eeten, Groen, Van Deurzen, Osterling and Van der Gass 2014). In our results, statistically significant differences in the expression of behavioral problems with respect to gender in persons with ASD were not observed, both on total and on individual scores.

When it comes to the impact of the age of people with ASD on behavioral problems, the results of numerous studies vary. Some studies report that younger adults with ASD exhibit more externalized behavioral problems than older adults, with some proving the opposite (Fortuna, Robinson, Smith, Meccarello, Bullen, Nobis and Davidson 2016; Wise, Smith and Rabins 2017). These results are inconsistent with our results, which is that age does not appear to be a statistically significant predictor of pragmatic functioning and severity of behavioral problems, which is consistent with the results of individual studies (Kats, Payne, Parlier and Piven 2013).

Numerous studies indicate that behavioral problems are not only one of the key problems in people with ASD, but are significantly associated with a degree of intellectual disability and show that persons with a higher degree of intellectual disability exhibit more behavioral problems (Matson, Hess and Boisjoli 2012). These results are consistent with the results we obtained. Hull, Mandy, and Petrides (2017) review the theoretical framework for these results and state that intellectual impairment is a significant predictor affecting the manifestation of all key symptoms of autism spectrum disorders, most notably those related to communication and behavioral problems. Deficiencies in cognitive functioning also explain the heterogeneous nature of difficulties in pragmatic functioning (Martin and McDonald 2003).

The results of our research also show that educational attainment is a significant predictor when it comes to behavioral problems, since people involved in the educational process have more opportunities to learn acceptable behavior patterns, interact more with peers, and broaden their social circles. They are taught to respect authority and social norms. Woodman, Smith, Greenberg and Mailick (2016) also found that education and family context were the most significant predictors of behavioral problems for people with ASD, as well as many other authors who have dealt with this type of research (Chowdhury, Benson and Hillier 2010; Matson and Horovitz 2010).

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results we can conclude the level of development of pragmatic competencies is a significant predictor of the manifestation of behavioral problems in adults with ASD. Variables Communicative Functions, Contextual Variations have a significant individual contribution to prediction, with a slightly higher individual contribution to prediction being the Interaction/Conversation variable. Educational attainment and intellectual disability are significant predictors of behavioral problems in adults with autism spectrum disorders. These results suggest that screening for lifelong behavioral problems in the population of people with ASD is needed, both for those with intellectual disabilities and those without, and for providing adequate support and rehabilitation programs.

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